

Cellular-Mobile Network in Global Communication

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Abstract: Cellular network is a communication technology for mobile phones or mobile stations. The mobile station (MS) consists of a cellphone equipment such as the radio transceiver, the digital signal processor, and the SIM card. The paper focuses on the global system for mobile communication (GSM) and its operations.

Keywords: mobile station, cellphone tower, mobile number, SIM card

1. Introduction

A cell phone, mobile phone, mobile station is a portable telephone that is used to make and receive calls at anytime and from anywhere. A mobile phone uses the GSM network and works on the radio frequency for receiving and transmitting information such as text message, voice message, and audio-video information.

2. Cellular Networks

Cellular network or mobile network is a telecommunication network that is used to exchange text/voice/audio/video messages between the mobile phones. The GSM Architecture shown in Figure 1 refers to the cellular networks [1].

Figure 1. GSM Architecture.

Figure 2. Cellular Tower

The cellular tower (base station) shown in Figure 2 has electronic equipment and antennas that is used to send and receive calls between the cell phones. The base station is a part of the GSM architecture [1]. The global system for mobile communication (GSM) [2] consists of three subsystems: the radio subsystem (RSS), the network switching subsystem (NSS), and the operation subsystem (OSS). In the author's previous paper, these subsystems (RSS, NSS, OSS) were explained precisely.

3. Conclusion

In this article, how a cell phone, mobile phone, or mobile station sends and receives calls has been explained along with the cellular tower.

References

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